

TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DISTRIBUTION OF ELECTRIC POWER PRODUCTIVITY IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Nigeria's electric power sector faces significant challenges in ensuring efficient and reliable distribution of electricity. This study examines the impact of technological factors on the productivity of electric power distribution in Osun State, Nigeria. Using a mixed-method approach, the research investigates the relationships between technological factors, such as grid modernization, automation, and the productivity of electric power distribution. The findings indicate that the adoption of advanced technologies (such as management of process control, power restoration, training, safety, etc.) could significantly enhance the efficiency and reliability of electric power distribution. The study also highlights the need to address the challenges of inadequate infrastructure, limited technical expertise, and high maintenance costs. The paper concludes with recommendations for policymakers, regulators, and industry stakeholders to promote the adoption of advanced technologies and improve the productivity of electric power distribution in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Electric power distribution, Productivity, Technological factors, Grid modernization.*

1.0 Introduction

The energy sector plays a vital role in a nation's socio-economic development, significantly contributing to increased productivity and a higher standard of living. Among the sub-sectors within the energy sector, electricity has the most profound impact on citizens' daily lives (IEA, 2020). The reliable supply and distribution of electricity have become increasingly crucial in recent years, given the essential role electricity plays in modern life. However, Nigeria's erratic power supply continues to hinder the country's economic and industrial growth, emphasizing the need for a stable and reliable electricity supply (World Bank, 2020).

The efficient operation of a power system requires the modification of certain characteristics, such as voltage, current, frequency, and power factor, at various points in the system. This is achieved through the use of a substation, which is a combination of specialized equipment. For instance, the voltage generated at a power station (typically between 11 and 25 kV) is stepped up to a higher voltage (usually 330 or 132 kV) using a step-up transformer for efficient transmission (Sankar, 2020). The substation, which includes equipment such as transformers, protection devices, control systems, and metering devices, plays a crucial role in delivering electricity to consumers at the required voltage level. In Nigeria, this is typically achieved at the 33/11 kV voltage level. Finally, near the consumer's location, the voltage is stepped down to the utilization level (415/240 V) using suitable apparatus in the substation.

Electricity distribution is the final stage of the electric power delivery process, which consists of power generation, power transmission, and power distribution (Hossain *et al.*, 2020). The distribution system is responsible for delivering electric power from transmission stations to local consumers. This involves taking electricity from high-voltage transmission circuits and delivering it to customers through a network of distribution substations, transformers, and power lines (Chen *et al.*, 2020). Distribution substations play a crucial role in this process by connecting to the transmission system and stepping down the transmission voltage to a medium voltage, typically ranging between 2 kV and 35 kV as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The generation, transmission and distribution of electric power schematic representation to the consumer (industrial, commercial and residential consumers) and the individual voltage level is also indicated appropriately on a single-line.

Source: NERC (2015)

The distribution system encompasses the electrical infrastructure between the substation and the consumer's meters, ensuring safe and reliable delivery of electricity to end-users. Electrical disturbances that compromise electrical power quality can result in substantial losses for energy consumers, with industries being the most severely impacted. These disruptions can cause equipment connected to the electrical power to malfunction, catch fire, or interrupt production processes, leading to significant economic losses (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). The impact of voltage unbalance on 3-phase induction motors has been extensively researched, with a focus on equipment efficiency and economic aspects influenced by losses (Singh *et al.*, 2020). Notably, oversizing motor specifications can also affect energy consumption.

Statement of Research Problem

The development of appropriate mitigation strategies for electric power distribution in Osun State are hampered by limited analyses on the power distribution infrastructure in the area. Long period interruption or the absence of energy for an extended period of time is inconvenient and has a negative impact on productivity. As a result of these, this research work concentrated on the technological factors influencing the distribution of electric power distribution in one of the distribution companies in South-western Nigeria known as Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (IBEDC). Specifically, it is imperative to investigate the technological factors that characterise the operations of the primary distribution stations in the study area. Hence this study.

History of Electricity in Nigeria

The history of electricity in Nigeria dates back to the early 20th century, with the first generating plant commissioned in 1916 in Lagos (Oyedepo, 2020). The plant had a capacity of 1.2 MW and was managed by the Nigerian Electricity Supply Company (NESCO) (Adefarati & Bassi, 2019). In the 1920s, electricity generation expanded to other parts of the country, including Kaduna, Kano, and Ibadan. In the 1950s, the Nigerian government established the Electricity Corporation of Nigeria (ECN) to oversee the development of the electricity sector. The ECN was responsible for generating, transmitting, and distributing electricity across the country. In 1972, the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) was established, and it took over the responsibility of generating electricity from the ECN. In the 1980s, the Nigerian government introduced the National Electric Power Policy (NEPP), which aimed to increase electricity generation and distribution across the country. The NEPP led to the establishment of the National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) in 1989, which replaced the ECN (Oyedepo, 2020).

In 2005, the Nigerian government introduced the Electric Power Sector Reform (EPSR) Act, which aimed to reform the electricity sector and increase private sector participation. The EPSR Act led to the establishment of the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) and the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN). In 2013, the Nigerian government privatized the PHCN and established 11 distribution companies, 6-generation companies, and 1 transmission company. The privatization aimed to increase efficiency and private sector participation in the electricity sector (Adefarati & Bassi, 2019).

2.0 Research Methodology

The study areas covered electric power distribution stations in selected local government areas (LGAs) in Osun state, Nigeria. Two zones were selected (Ile-Ife and Osogbo zones) and the Local government area selected from Ile-Ife were Ife North, Ife South, Ife Central, Ife East and Olorunda LGAs were selected from Osogbo. The LGAs in Ife zone were being selected because of the high level of electricity consumption recorded there while the Olorunda LGA in Osogbo hosts the Transmission Company of Nigeria, National Control Centre in Osogbo. A set of questionnaires were administered to the 5 primary distribution stations in the selected LGAs and these were purposively chosen for the study. A total of 40 respondents were also selected as respondents in both regional headquarters (Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company in Ile-Ife and Osogbo).

3.0 Results and Discussion

Socio-economic and Demographics of Respondents

The results of the socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the respondents are as presented on Table 1. The results showed that 15 % of the respondents were within the ages of 21-30 years, 35 % of the respondents were between the ages of 31-40 years while 45 % of the respondents within the study area were within the ages of 41-50 years and 5 % of the respondents were above 50 years. This implies that most of the respondents were presently in their productive age and therefore, with training and good materials in their field of work there would be effectiveness and efficiency in distribution of electricity to the end user.

The result in Table 1 further reveals that about 20% of the respondents have NCE/OND, about 60% are HND/BSc holders, 20% have completed PGD/MSc education while no one has PhD degree. Therefore, all the members of technical staff in the distribution company had one form of formal educational certificate or the other. Some of them even had one or two certificates in one professional course or the other. Literacy is believed to have a positive impact on the efficient use of productive resources and adoption of technology, in the case of electric power distribution, technological literacy educates individuals to make well-informed choices in their capacity as workers.

Expectedly, education plays a vital role in the development of any economic sector, as supported by the theory of planned behaviour as it equips its recipients with skills for identifying proper business management, financial management, proper marketing and avoidance of business failure (Sinan *et al.*, 2018). The result revealed that 10 % of the respondents had below five years of service, 55 % of the respondents had 5-10 years of service and 35 % of the respondents within the study area had above 10 years of service in the power distribution sector. Work experience is a chance to look into different job options for improved self-awareness, maturity, independence, and self-assurance. Increased desire to continue studying and/or receive additional training.

This means that many of the respondents have what it takes to work successfully in electric power distribution. The more experienced one is, the higher the technological capability and the lower the profit inefficiency (Takeshima *et al.*, 2014). The electric power skills as shown in Table 1 is as follows, 5% of the respondents are beginner/casual workers, 15 % covered intermediate while the remaining 80 % of the respondents are professionals. Professionalism in the workplace ensures good performance, portrays the correct corporate image, motivates employees, ensures justice and fairness, increases success rates, improves customer connections, and establishes strong company standards (Smith and Mckeen, 2003; and Brandon-Jones, 2017). The technical department is mainly divided into two namely, network planning and design, and operation and maintenance. The operation and maintenance is subdivided into electrical fitting, cable jointing, control room and dispatch centre. 5% of the respondents in both regional headquarters cover the technical engineer, 10% of the respondents are the operation and maintenance, 5% of the respondents are in network planning and design and 25% and 15% are in the control room and dispatch centre respectively.

Table 1: Socio-demographic and Organisational characteristics

Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage (%)
1. Sex	Male	38	95
	Female	2	5
2. Age	21 – 30	6	15
	31 – 40	14	35
	41 – 50	18	45
	Above 50	2	5
3. Educational qualification	NCE/OND	8	20
	HND/BSC	24	60
	PGD/MSC	8	20
4. Year of service	Below 5yr	4	10
	5 - 10yrs	22	55
	Above 10yrs	14	35
5. Electric power skill	Beginner/casual	2	5
	Intermediate	6	15
	Professional	32	80
6. Department	Technical engineer	2	5
	Operation and maintenance	20	10

Network planning and design	2	5
Control room	10	25
Dispatch centre	6	15

Due to the matter of high importance of technical staff to always be in the control room in order to keep eyes on the equipment there and pass information to the dispatch centre for escalation if there is fault or malfunction. The high percentage there is because of their operation on shift duty. Invariably, this means that there might be less or no effect on the side of the technical workers on the defect of power distribution to the customers in the study area.

Electric Power Distribution Capabilities of Injection Substations in Selected Local Government Areas in Osun State, Nigeria

The results of the locations, LGA covered, capacity and quantity, status and year of completion of the injection substation in selected local government areas in Osun State, Nigeria are presented in Table 2. It is clearly stated there that each injection substation is located in each local government area. All injection substations are fully operational except one out of the two 15 MVA, 33/11 kV installed at Ondo road, Modakeke-Ife which was not operational but the other power transformer was working at optimal level. The overall available capacity of the substations is 92.5 MVA and the overall capacity in operation is 77.5 MVA which gives the overall capacity in operation at 83.78 %.

Table 2: Injection Substation Capacity in Selected Local Government Areas in Osun State, Nigeria

S / N	Location	LGA Covered	Capacity (MVA)	Quantity	Status	Year completed
1	Opp. AP filling station, Ile-Ife	Ife Central and part of Ife East	15	2	Fully Operational	2005
2	Power line area, Osogbo	Olorunda	15	1	Fully Operational	2008
3	Ondo road, Modakeke-Ife	Ife East	15	2	Only one is operational	2010
4	Around Moro junction, Moro	Ife North	2.5	1	Fully Operational	2014
5	Beside OAUTHC, Ile-Ife	Ife South	7.5	2	Fully Operational	2015

Table 3 shows the average value of power expected, power received and power output in six (6) years. There was great amount of power losses over the six years for instance, in the year 2018 the difference between the average power expected and the average power output is 8.60 MW and the following year was 5.87 MW followed by 4.80 MW in the year 2021 where the least amount of power loss in the six years was 4.55 MW. The table also revealed the power transaction of injection substations in the Ife zone and Olorunda from 2018 to 2023. There was a wide gap between the average power expected and average power output starting in 2018 (16 %) and reduced in the year 2019 (14 %) then, it was a bit steady. The power losses over the year was proof of effect on operation of electric power distribution which was as a result of the technological factors influencing the productivity of electric power distribution.

Table 3: Power transaction of injection substation in MW over the year

S/N	Years	Average power expected (MW)	Average power received (MW)	Average power output (MW)
1	2018	23.71	18.93(79.84%)	15.11(63.74%)
2	2019	25.45	23.29(91.51%)	19.58(76.94%)
3	2020	26.78	23.58(88.05%)	21.98(82.08%)
4	2021	27.34	24.32(88.95%)	21.69(79.33%)
5	2022	27.91	25.89(92.76%)	23.36(83.70%)
6	2023	28.86	26.38(91.41%)	24.03(83.26%)

Factors Influencing the Productivity of Electric Power Distribution in the Study Area

a. Technological factor

Technological factors affecting the productivity of electricity distribution in the study area are discussed in the Table 4 below. For management of the workforce, the result revealed that 20 % of the workforce were never motivated and 40 % of the workforce were very rarely coordinated and planned for, while the majority of the workforce (52.5 %) have no good understanding of management of processes control (rarely). Though, the mean rating under management was below average (2 very rarely). All the factors under process (computerized equipment productivity, use of management information system and quick restoration of power) had a great effect on the technological factor with mean rating (never).

Table 4: Technological factor Influencing the Productivity of Electric Power Distribution in the Study Area

S/ N	Characteristics	Frequency (%)	Mean	Mean rating	
1	Managem ent	Workforce motivation	8 (20 %)	1	2.0000
		Planning and Coordination	16 (40 %)	2	
		Control of processes	21 (52.5 %)	3	
2	Process	Computerized equipment	10 (25 %)	1	1.3333
		Use of Management Information System	6 (15 %)	1	
		Quick restoration of power	18 (45 %)	2	
3	Work design	Better work method	28 (70 %)	4	4.0000
		Induction training	36 (90 %)	5	
		In-service and maintenance training	27 (67.5 %)	3	
4	Work environme nt	Better lightning and illumination	10 (25 %)	1	2.6667
		Better ventilation	27 (67.5 %)	3	
		Work-place safety	31 (77.5 %)	4	
5	Program	Total Quality Management	12 (30 %)	2	2.3333
		Incentive scheme	6 (15 %)	1	
		Suggestion scheme	33 (82.5 %)	4	

6	Technology	New technology used	14 (35 %)	2	2.3333
		Suggest acquisition of new technology	32 (80 %)	4	
		Acquisition of automation in assembly Surface Mount Technology	7 (17.5 %)	1	

Key: 5 point likert scale- 1 = Never; 2 = Very Rarely; 3 = Rarely; 4 = Occasionally; 5 = Frequently

b. Maintenance factor

Table 5a shows that 62.5 % of the respondents made it known that corrective maintenance was mostly done out of four types of maintenance practiced, the predictive has the lowest percentage of 7.5 % and preventive maintenance of 15 % showed that equipment was repaired or replaced after its expiration. There was malfunctioning or breakdown in most cases, which means there was poor maintenance culture of electric power distribution.

Preventive maintenance is the most important type of maintenance that should be practiced since it inspects, maintains, and protects equipment or facilities until they break down or develop other issues, but it was just 15 %. Table 5a also shows the type of circuit breaker used.

The air blast circuit breaker covered 60%, both vacuum, and sulfur fluoride circuit breakers were also 15 %, and bulk oil and minimum oil circuit breaker were both 5 %. The Table 5a also shows the type of relay used. 35% of the respondents revealed thermal relay was used, electromechanical 25 %, followed by solid state and reed relay of 15%, while hybrid was 10%. Table 5b shows that cleaning and removing carbon deposition, electrolytic clean covered the highest percentage of 70% while others were used on a rare occasion to clean and remove carbon deposition. Check, clean and tighten of components had 65% when necessary, read and fill magnetic oil gauge was 80% when necessary, 70% showed circuit breaker oil was also changed when necessary and grease for lubrication was 57.5% of low grade.

Table 5c shows the technical personnel on condition-based maintenance, 47.5% of the respondents showed that they had someone in-charge of it and the highest percentage of the technical staff were aware that the circuit breaker should be opened before the isolator, which had been confirmed for good work design.

The inability of the electric power distribution company to provide uninterrupted electric power for the use of the nation's citizenry is well documented. The ineffective operation and maintenance of injection substations in selected local government areas in Osun State has been attributed in part to the inadequacy of the electric power distribution capabilities in the area. The results showed that the total capacity of the injection substation in the study area should be more than 92.5MVA and all should be fully operational unlike the way it is, where 15MVA is not in operation. This is among the causes of the community's inconsistent power supply. The life cycle of the injection substation might still be intact because none of the substations has used up to its average life cycle from the findings made. From the results also, the average power expected over the year was rated according to their capacity at hand in which they can accommodate. It has an effect on average

Table 5a: Maintenance factor Influencing the Productivity of Electric Power Distribution in the Study Area

Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Type of maintenance practiced	Predictive	3	7.5
	Preventive	6	15
	Break down	6	15
	Corrective	25	62.5
Type of circuit breaker used	Bulk oil	2	5
	Minimum oil	2	5
	Sulfur Fluoride SF ₆	6	15
	Vacuum	6	15
	Air blast	24	60
	Hybrid	4	10
	Reed	6	15
Type of relay used	Solid state	6	15
	Electromechanical	10	25
	Thermal	14	35
Clean and remove carbon deposition	Acetone	2	5
	Kerosene	4	10

	Trichloroethy lene	6	15
	Electroclean	28	70

Table5b: Maintenance Factor Influencing the Productivity of Electric Power Distribution in the Study Area

S/N	Characteristics	Frequency			
		Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Necessary
1	Check, clean and tighten component	2 (5 %)	2 (5 %)	10 (25 %)	26 (65 %)
2	Read and fill magnetic oil gauge	4 (10 %)	2 (5 %)	2 (5 %)	32 80 %
3	Change circuit breaker oil	0 (0 %)	8 (20 %)	4 (10 %)	28 (70 %)
4	Grease grade for lubrication	Low	Medium	High	Very high
		23 (57.5 %)	14 (35 %)	3 (7.5 %)	0 (0 %)

Table 5c: Maintenance Factor Influencing the Productivity of Electric Power Distribution in the Study Area

S/N	Characteristics	Frequency	
		Yes	No
1	Technical personnel on condition-based maintenance	19 (47.5 %)	21 (52.5 %)
2	Open circuit breaker before isolator	38 (95 %)	2 (5 %)

power received with great difference due to the fact that sub-transmission stations cannot give what the distribution station is unable to receive. Therefore, the average power output was so low compared with the capacity of the injection substation and the average expected power.

Effective management is crucial for electric power distribution companies (DisCos) to overcome internal and external challenges. However, many DisCos struggle with planning oversights, hindering their ability to manage electricity distribution efficiently. Good management skills are essential for organizations to achieve their goals and objectives. The management skills like good technical skills (necessary for performing specific tasks and operations), Conceptual skills (required for planning, decision-making, and problem-solving) and human or interpersonal skills (essential for effective communication, motivation, and leadership) are essential for planning, communication, decision making, delegation, inspiring and problem-solving, in other to motivate staff, improve planning and coordination and effective process control.

4.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

In conclusion, the electric power distribution system in Osun State, Nigeria, faces significant challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, aging equipment, and limited ability to integrate renewable energy sources. To address these challenges, it is essential to modernize the distribution infrastructure through the adoption of smart grid technologies, advanced distribution management systems, and renewable energy integration.

Effective management practices, including motivated workforce, better planning, and coordination, are also crucial in improving the productivity and efficiency of electric power distribution. By addressing these challenges and adopting best practices, the electric power distribution system in Osun State can be transformed to provide reliable, efficient, and cost-effective electricity to meet the growing demand of users. A manager with strong management abilities can help the organization to accomplish its mission, vision, and business objectives with fewer obstacles.

Recommendations

To increase the quality of electricity delivered to customers in Osun State, there should be a good management system by promoting qualified workers as required which will compensate them for their hard work including planning, coordination and effective control of processes. The distribution company should always organize training programmes to empower and enrich their staff with adequate knowledge required for a good job in the area of maintenance, preventive maintenance to be precise.

Furthermore, distribution companies should establish a department to oversee the whole Utility Availability Centred Maintenance Strategy (UACMS), which is depicted as a flow chart/block diagram with various sections that fully explain the combination of preventive, predictive and corrective maintenance strategies and other modern maintenance techniques.

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